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Influence of Food Service Attributes on Consumer Buying Behavior

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ABSTRACT :

The study, titled "Influence of Food Service Attributes on Consumer Buying Behavior," examines specific food service attributes influence consumer buying behavior in a provincial setting. Localized Samgyeopsal, a Korean barbecue cuisine adapted to Filipino tastes and pricing, has seen a rise in popularity across Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. However, limited research has been conducted on how key restaurant attributes influence consumer intentions in rural areas, and many businesses are still relying on assumptions rather than consumer-based data. This study utilized a descriptive-quantitative design, gathering data through a Likert-scale questionnaire administered to 100 respondents across five selected Samgyeopsal restaurants in Cabiao using quota sampling. Statistical tools such as weighted mean and Spearman's rank correlation coefficient were used to analyze the relationship between food service attributes and consumer buying behavior.

The results showed significant correlations between these attributes and all three behavioral constructs of TPB, indicating strong correlations between food service attributes and consumer buying behavior. The results underscore that improving specific food service attributes can definitely influence the attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control of patronizing localized samgyeopsal Korean cuisine restaurants. This highlights that localized samgyeopsal restaurants and local business owners to align their offerings and operational strategies on consumer-driven data rather than assumptions to further improve customer satisfaction, loyalty and the long-term stability and success of the business.

1. Introduction

The food service industry has gone through a large-scale evolution with the changing consumer tastes and cuisines across the world, reflecting globally. One of which is the emerging popularity of Korean culture here in our country, as reflected by the kind of food Filipinos eat, as Samgyeopsal has become a popular dining choice among Filipinos. As for Argarin (2021), most Filipinos have been open to Korean culture over the past few years in terms of their music, fashion, beauty care products, and, naturally, food, most notably the most sought-after "Samgyeopsal", which led to the mass opening of Korean restaurants nationwide⁵. In the long run, in places such as Cabiao, Nueva Ecija, local businessmen have addressed this by providing localized versions of Samgyeopsal, modifying the taste, ingredients, service and prices to suit what will appeal to the local market. Even with the trend, little is known about what particular restaurant characteristics drive consumers to select and repeat visit these restaurants. In accordance with Rechner (2023), understanding consumer purchasing behavior is vital for companies to stay competitive, particularly in markets such as the food service sector, where customer tastes and satisfaction are paramount²⁰.

However, despite the popularity of Samgyeopsal there is a notable lack of research on consumer buying behavior toward localized Korean cuisine in rural or provincial areas like Cabiao. The majority of previous research, for example, that by Babierra et al. (2021), concentrated mainly on consumer satisfaction in metropolitan Korean restaurants, highlighted service quality and atmosphere in urban areas⁶. Likewise, Ong et.al (2023) investigated what consumers eat but did not carry their analysis to the smaller towns, where consumer populations and purchasing capacities can be very different¹⁸. As per Cayaban et al. (2023), little research exists linking Filipino consumer decisions and their dining experiences with Korean food, especially in provinces such as Nueva Ecija⁷. Moreover, small business food enterprises and other enterprises in provinces such as Cabiao often trade without customer data-informed insights, which can lead to business failure. They could aid them in determining consumer tastes and enhancing their business strategies. As mentioned by Duong et al. (2021), most local firms in emerging economies still operate based on assumptions and not consumer-based facts; hence, shaping offerings to effectively and strategically meet local needs is challenging¹⁰.

This research study analyzed the influence of food service attributes on consumer buying behavior towards localized samgyeopsal Korean cuisine in Cabiao. To fill the gap, this research aimed to analyze how food service attributes, notably the quality of food and beverages, quality of service, quality of setting and price and value influence consumer buying behavior in localized samgyeopsal Korean cuisine in Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. Acquiring insights into customer preferences within the food service industry is essential to developing effective marketing and operational strategies. By focusing on consumers in a provincial setting, the study seeks to provide data that can help and guide local business owners in improving their services and better meeting customer expectations. Moreover, the findings of this study may serve as a helpful reference for business owners in identifying which food service attributes significantly influence consumer buying behavior and that can help guide and create well-informed decisions for businesses and enhance the overall competitiveness and sustainability of localized samgyeopsal Korean cuisine restaurants.

2. Research Method

2.1 Research Design

This study used both descriptive-survey methods and a quantitative research design. The descriptive-survey method is appropriate for collecting relevant data systematically on circumstances or phenomena as they usually happen, not by controlling any variables. The quantitative design aspect of this study requires the use of a survey questionnaire, enabling the collection of numerical data from a defined sample population. This combined approach is suitable because it allows the researchers to describe, measure, and analyze the current buying behaviors of consumers toward localized Samgyeopsal Korean cuisine in Cabiao, Nueva Ecija.

2.2 Participants

The researchers used quota sampling, a non-probability sampling technique in which individuals have been picked based on specified criteria to ensure that specific features correctly reflect their prevalence in the population. This technique ensures that each restaurant is fairly represented in the study. The researchers of the study particularly selected five establishments, such as Jeju Korean Grill House, Sissy Unli Samgyeopsal and Unli Wings 199, CABS Korean Restaurant, Sam-chi Foodhouse, and Queen of Wings, based on their popularity, accessibility, and consistent customer flow. The researchers of the study surveyed a sample size of 100 customers, evenly distributed across the five establishments, which consisted of 20 customers per restaurant. Since these establishments' customer count is uncertain, it is because they do not maintain and account for the total number of customers per visit.

2.3 Instrumentation

The instrument used in this study was a research-made questionnaire designed for the purpose of gathering data. The questionnaire will have four essential parts and is created to gather demographic profiles and respondents' perceptions and behavior towards localized samgyeopsal Korean cuisine. The first part of the questionnaire is the demographic profile of the respondents. The second part will be the Food Service Attributes of localized samgyeopsal Korean cuisine. The third part is the Consumer Buying Behavior based on the TPB, which focuses on the respondents' behavioral responses. The research survey questionnaire uses a 5-point Likert scale to measure the levels of agreement, where (1) indicates strongly disagree, (2) refers to disagree, (3) refers to somewhat agree, (4) refers to agree, and (5) refers to strongly agree.

2.4 Validation of Instrument

The researchers employed content validity so that the questionnaire would accurately capture the food service attributes constructs as well as consumer buying behavior constructs. To establish the content validity, the researchers sought the expertise of professionals, the validators make sure that the questions in the questionnaire were relevant and adequate to study the impact of food service characteristics on consumer purchase behavior in the food sector.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedures

The data gathering procedure began with the researchers preparing and endorsing a letter of consent to be delivered to the owners or managers of localized samgyeopsal Korean cuisine restaurants in Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. Once the letter was approved, the researchers proceeded providing survey questionnaires to 20 respondents from each of the five restaurants. The distribution of the questionnaire lasted for more than two weeks until the quota was reached.

2.6 Analysis of Data

The information gathered in this study was arranged and used the research design as a guide. The researchers employed the Weighted Mean to determine respondents' ratings of food service attributes and buying behavior among consumers, while Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient determines the correlation between these variables. The Likert Scale was utilized as an instrument for interpreting levels of agreement in the questionnaire.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter includes a thorough presentation and discussion of data analysis and results from 100 respondents across five restaurants. The survey's data were provided in tabular form with supporting interpretations, literature, and studies.

Table 1
Respondents' Level of Agreement on Food Service Attributes
of Localized Samgyeopsal Korean Cuisine.

Respondents' Level of Agreement on Food Service Attributes of Localized Samgyeopsal Korean Cuisine	WM	VI
Quality of Food and Beverages	4.43	Strongly Agree
Quality of Service	4.23	Strongly Agree
Quality of Setting	4.25	Strongly Agree
Price and Value	4.24	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.29	Strongly Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree; 4.21 - 5.00, Agree; 4.20 - 3.41, Somewhat Agree; 3.40 - 2.61, Disagree; 2.60 - 1.81, Strongly Disagree; 1.80 - 1.00

Table 1 presents the respondents' level of agreement on food service attributes of Localized Samgyeopsal Korean Cuisine, with an overall weighted mean of 4.29 and the verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree." The respondents' level of agreement on the food service attributes of Localized Samgyeopsal Korean Cuisine, in terms of Quality of Food and Beverages with a weighted mean of 4.43, Quality of Setting with a weighted mean of

4.25, Price and Value with a weighted mean of 4.24, and Quality of Service with a weighted mean of 4.23.

Table 2
Respondents' Level of Agreement on their Level of Food Service Attributes Influence Consumer Buying Behavior

Respondents' Level of Agreement on their Level of Food Service Attributes Influence Consumer Buying Behavior	WM	VI
Attitudes	4.27	Strongly Agree
Subjective Norms	4.27	Strongly Agree
Perceived Behavioral Control	4.36	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.30	Strongly Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree; 4.21 - 5.00, Agree; 4.20 - 3.41, Somewhat Agree; 3.40 - 2.61, Disagree; 2.60 - 1.81, Strongly Disagree; 1.80 - 1.00

Table 2 presents the respondents' level of agreement on how Food Service Attributes Influence Consumer Buying Behavior at Localized Samgyeopsal Korean Cuisine Restaurants, with an overall weighted mean of 4.30, and the verbal interpretation "Strongly Agree." In perceived behavioral control, it had a weighted mean of 4.36, Attitudes had a weighted mean of 4.27, and Subjective Norms had a weighted mean of 4.27.

Table 3
Significant Correlation Between the Food Service Attributes of Localize Samgyeopsal Korean Cuisine and Consumer Buying Behavior.

INDICATORS	P-VALUE	DECISION	CONCLUSION
Quality of Food and Beverages	0.004	Reject Ho	Significant
Quality of Service	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Quality of Setting	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Price and Value	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Overall	0.004	Reject Ho	Significant

Legend: If P-Value=<0.05-Reject Ho (Significant); If P-Value>0.05-Accept Ho (Not Significant)

Table 3 presented the significant correlation of food service attributes of localized samgyeopsal Korean cuisine to consumer buying behavior with an overall P-value of 0.004. Findings showed that the P-Value of quality of food and beverages, quality of service, quality of setting, and price and value (0.004, <.001, <.001, <.001) was less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis was "Rejected," and the relationship between the food service attributes and consumer buying behavior was "Significant."

4. Conclusion

The following conclusions are derived from the findings above:

- 4.1. The respondents strongly agreed on all the food service attributes of localized samgyeopsal Korean cuisine in terms of quality of food and beverages, quality of service, quality of setting, and price and value.
- 4.2. The respondents strongly agreed that the food service attributes influence consumer buying behavior in terms of attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.
- 4.3. The researchers rejected the null hypothesis and therefore there was a significant correlation between the food service attributes and consumer buying behavior.

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